

Dry laser-assisted fabrication of F-doped graphene electrodes: Boosting performance of Zn-ion hybrid capacitors

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ABSTRACT

Laser-assisted direct deposition of graphene on desired substrates has emerged as a versatile method for a wide range of applications. This “dry” and eco-friendly approach is effective for fabricating electrode materials for high-performance electrochemical energy storage devices. Herein, we introduce a novel laser-assisted explosive synthesis and transfer technique to synthesize, transfer, and deposit fluorine-doped graphene-like structures in a single step by irradiating a single precursor. Operating under ambient conditions, this method enables the deposition of the electrode material directly onto the current collector, avoiding manual transfer steps. Our electrochemical evaluation revealed significant improvements in zinc-ion capacitor performance, with the fluorine-doped graphene-like cathode achieving a discharge capacity of $19.5 \mu\text{Ah cm}^{-2}$ at 1 mA cm^{-2} and energy density of $10.93 \mu\text{Wh cm}^{-2}$ at $92 \mu\text{W cm}^{-2}$. Density functional theory simulations elucidated the local bonding arrangement, particularly between Zn^{2+} ions and the F-doped graphene sheets, addressing issues related to device degradation over long-term operation, as the device retains $\sim 65\%$ of its initial energy density after 10,000 cycles. Our results demonstrate the potential of this laser-assisted, industrially-relevant process for the direct deposition of graphene-based materials as superior electrodes for energy storage applications, offering a scalable and sustainable alternative to conventional wet-chemistry methods.

1. Introduction

Graphene-like porous structures have demonstrated superior performance in numerous applications over the past years. For many cases, such as gas sensing or electrochemical energy storage, adding adatoms appears to be a viable and promising strategy to enhance their performance.[1,2] Doping with fluorine, the most electronegative element, can endow graphene with remarkable chemical, tribological, and electronic characteristics.[3–5] Depending on the synthesis method used,[6,7] and the local distribution and density of fluorine,[8,9] the carbon atoms linked to fluorine can have either sp^3 (covalent C-F) or sp^2 (ionic or semi-ionic C-F) hybridization.

Fluorinated graphene can be synthesized using either direct fluorination or exfoliation of fluorinated graphite.[10] Direct gas fluorination often requires toxic and very corrosive gases such as F_2 or XeF_2 . [3,11] Plasma-assisted fluorination relies on expensive equipment,[10] and the

ion bombardment that is involved can induce damage the carbon structure.[12] Further, typical N_2/F_2 gas-assisted fluorination requires very long processing times, of the order of few days.[13] Hydrothermal/solvothermal methods also require hazardous and corrosive reagents such as HF.[14] While liquid phase exfoliation (LPE) of fluorinated graphite (FG) may use eco-friendly intercalating molecules,[15,16] in many cases harmful solvents are used (such as NMP,[17] ACN or DMF [18]). The information presented underscores the pressing need for innovative synthesis techniques of fluorinated graphene that are not only scalable but also environmentally conscious.

Laser-based methods have recently emerged as they provide a versatile and cost-effective approach towards the “green” graphitization of various carbon sources.[19–22] Ye et al. synthesized fluorinated nanodiamonds and graphene-like structures in powder form, after irradiating polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) with a $9.3 \mu\text{m}$ CO_2 laser inside a 3 atm Ar chamber, showing that both the inert atmosphere and the higher

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pressure were essential for this process.[23] Li et al. prepared superhydrophobic fluorinated graphene-like structures, using the same laser source to irradiate polyimide inside a chamber under the purging of SF₆ gas.[24] Similar to the conventional chemical synthesis processes discussed above, these laser-based approaches either operate under conditions that restrict scalable production or utilize precursors that are not environmentally benign, as non-toxic SF₆ has a high global warming potential.

Recently, we developed a novel scalable method, operating at ambient conditions, for the deposition of graphene-based films on any type of substrate, including soft materials (polymers, textiles, etc.), metals, glass, ceramics, and so on.[25,26] This method is based on the laser-mediated explosive synthesis and transfer (LEST) of graphene-related materials.[25] The precursor materials include various carbon sources that upon transformation by the laser beam, are able to produce proper streams of propelling gasses able to transfer the graphene flakes onto the selected substrate. The advantages of the LEST process over competing methods, such as direct laser graphene scribing (commonly referred to as LIG), have been discussed in detail elsewhere.[25] In summary, these advantages can be outlined as follows: LIG provides a straightforward method for converting carbon precursors, primarily polyimide (Kapton) into graphene. However, it is primarily limited to surface conversions, binding the graphene film to the polymer substrate. This creates challenges when graphene needs to be transferred to another substrate for specific applications. The transfer process is typically manual, involving steps that risk contamination and deterioration of the properties of graphene. In contrast, LEST induces an explosive reaction that simultaneously synthesizes and transfers high-quality graphene onto any target substrate. This combined synthesis-and-transfer approach allows for the use of diverse carbon sources and substrates, enabling the production of graphene films with well-controlled properties and simplifying fabrication, particularly for advanced electronic applications. The versatility of the method stands on the fact that the simultaneous irradiation/transformation of two precursors, results to graphene-based materials that can be either doped with heteroatoms or decorated with other compounds, e.g., metal oxide nanoparticles.

In the current study, we utilize the LEST approach to synthesize and transfer high quality fluorinated graphene-like porous films, originating from the laser-assisted decomposition of a fluoropolymer precursor material. The entire process takes place under ambient conditions, eliminating the need for wet-chemistry or the use of hazardous gases. High-resolution transmission electron microscopy supports that the synthesized structures are composed of few layered graphene stacks, with an increased interlayer spacing in relation to that of Bernal-stacked graphite. These F-doped graphene-like films were used as binder-free cathode materials in a zinc-ion hybrid supercapacitor (ZIC), to benefit from the interaction between C-F and the metal cations.[27] Our findings suggest that the introduction of even a small amount of fluorine in the carbon cathode, can substantially improve the performance of the ZIC. As far as we are aware, our work presents the first report on the laser-assisted growth and transfer of few-layered fluorinated graphene structures achieved at ambient conditions.

2. Methods

2.1. Preparation of LEST fluorinated graphene-like (LEST-FG) electrodes

The laser-assisted preparation of the fluorinated graphene-like films is schematically depicted in Scheme 1. The precursor used, is in the form of a laminate (Lohmann) composed of three layers: the middle layer, 25 μm thick polyimide foil (PI) is sandwiched between two films of fluorinated ethylene propylene (FEP) polymer, with each one being 2.5 μm thick. The selected precursor, combining polyimide (Kapton) and FEP in a balanced mass ratio, is an optimal choice to ensure high-quality graphene formation with effective F atom doping. The high absorption of

Scheme 1. Schematic representation of Laser-mediated Explosive Synthesis and Transfer (LEST) of fluorinated graphene-like structures.

Kapton engenders the heat increase needed for graphene synthesis, while the thin FEP layers enable efficient heating and decomposition through the thermal influence of Kapton. This sandwich-type layer structure enhances the interaction, achieving the desired properties. A Nd:YAG laser operating at 1064 nm with 1.5 ms pulse width, was used to simultaneously decompose the precursor and transfer the fluorinated graphene flakes onto the desired substrate, which was placed 1 mm below the precursor. Four different laser beam fluence values were utilized (49, 60, 74, and 104 J cm⁻²). A large area spot size, of 1.4 mm in diameter was used for all experiments, to allow large surface coverage and hence fast scribing. The laser beam was fixed, while the substrates were placed onto a biaxial X-Y translation stage. The stage movement speed was 2 mm s⁻¹, and the laser pulse repetition rate was 2 Hz, resulting to a pulse overlap of ~ 33 %. The materials created are designated as “LEST-FG-y”, where “y” represents the specific laser fluence utilized, with values including 49, 60, 74, and 104. The fluorine-free LEST-G-74 cathode that was used in the reference device, was prepared in a similar manner, by replacing the FEP//PI/FEP laminate with a neat PI foil, as described in our previous work.[28] All samples were fabricated in ambient environment. The typical thickness of the LEST depositions is at least of some tens of microns,[25,26] while the mass loading achieved is ~ 0.5 mg cm⁻².

2.2. Physicochemical characterization

The texture of the LEST-FG-y films was studied using a high-resolution field-emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) instrument (Zeiss, SUPRA 35VP) operated at 10 kV. A high-resolution field-emission transmission electron microscope (HR-TEM, Thermo Fischer Scientific, Talos F200i) operated at 200 kV was utilized to examine the microstructure of the samples, which were prepared by drop casting 5 μl of aqueous suspension of the material onto holey carbon support copper TEM grids.

Raman spectroscopy was performed using a micro-Raman system (Jobin Yvon, T-64000). The laser line of 514 nm was selected, and a microscope objective of 50 × magnification was used. The wavelength scale of the acquired Raman spectra was calibrated using the ~ 520 cm⁻¹ band of crystalline Si. The laser power on sample was set below 1 mW.

The surface chemistry of LEST-FG-y samples was explored with X-ray and Ultraviolet Photoelectron Spectroscopies (XPS/UPS). Experiments were conducted in an ultra-high vacuum (5×10^{-10} mbar) chamber, equipped with a hemispherical electron analyzer (SPECS, Phoibos 100-1D-DLD) and a non-monochromatized dual Mg/Al x-ray gun. XP spectra were recorded with MgK α (1253.6 eV), and an analyzer pass energy of 10 eV resulting to a FWHM of 0.85 eV for Ag3d5/2. The UP spectra were acquired using HeI irradiation (21.22 eV), produced by a UV source (model UVS 10/35). The analyzer operated in the constant retarding ratio (CRR) mode, with CRR = 10. The samples were subjected to a bias of -12.29 V to shift the spectra from the spectrometer threshold. For the XPS measurements, the samples LEST-FG-y were deposited on Mo foil and were measured without any pretreatment. X-ray diffraction was conducted with a Bruker D8 Advance instrument, utilizing a nickel filtered CuK α radiation source (1.5406 Å), operated at 40 kV and 40 mA.

Nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms at 77 K were acquired with a Quantachrome Autosorb iQ instrument, and the samples were outgassed at 120 °C for 2 h. The specific surface area and the pore size distribution of mesopores were calculated with the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method and the Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) method, respectively. Sheet resistance was measured for LEST-FG-y films deposited on glass slides using as prepared films, of 1×1 cm² area, using a four-point probe system (Ossila). For the wettability tests a homemade setup was used, which consisted of a x-y-z- stage, an optical track, and a camera. The volume of the water droplet was 10 μ L.

2.3. Assembly of zinc-ion hybrid capacitors

Swagelok type cells were prepared using 1 M Zn(CH₃COO)₂ aqueous electrolyte. A laser fluence of 74 J cm⁻² was selected in the LEST process, to deposit LEST-FG-74 on both the front and the back side of carbon fiber paper (Sigracet 29AA non-woven PTFE-free, thickness of ~ 190 μ m), which served as the current collector. Afterwards, a 9 mm diameter disk was punched from double-side coated carbon fiber paper and used as the cathode of the device. The anode was Zn foil (Alfa Aesar) of 9 mm diameter, 99.98 % purity, 250 μ m thickness. It was used as obtained, being subjected only to ethanol rinsing. The two electrodes were separated using two Dreamweaver Titanium T 0.58/30 (GLATFELTER) membranes, each of which was 30 μ m thick.

2.4. Electrochemical evaluation of zinc-ion hybrid capacitors

All electrochemical experiments were conducted at room temperature. An Autolab PGSTAT302N potentiostat/galvanostat, equipped with an FRA32 frequency response analyzer module, was used for the cyclic voltammetry (CV) and the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). EIS was performed in the range of 0.01 Hz to 100 kHz, using a perturbation amplitude of 5 mV, at the open circuit voltage. For the acquisition of galvanostatic charging/discharging (GCD) curves, and the conduction of the cycling stability test, a CTS Standard system (BaSyTec GmbH) was used. The CV/GCD experiments were performed 24 h post-assembly of the ZICs, whereas EIS spectra were recorded at specific intervals, i.e. immediately post-assembly (0 h), as well as 4 h and 23 h thereafter.

The areal capacity of the device was determined through its discharge characteristics, using the following equation:

$$C[\mu\text{Ah cm}^{-2}] = \frac{I\Delta t}{3.6A} \quad (1)$$

where I [mA] is the applied current, A [cm²] is the geometric area of the device, and Δt [s] is the discharge duration.

The areal energy and power densities were calculated using the integrated area of the discharge part of the GCD curve, as follows:

$$E[\text{mWh cm}^{-2}] = \frac{1}{3600A} \int_0^{t_d} IV dt \quad (2)$$

$$P[\text{mW cm}^{-2}] = 3600 \frac{E[\text{mWh cm}^{-2}]}{\Delta t} \quad (3)$$

2.5. Computational method and details

The B3LYP hybrid density functional approach,[29] which combines density functional and Hartree-Fock methods and uses Becke's three-parameter exchange functional[30] with the Lee-Yang-Parr correlation function[31] and its long-range corrected version using the Coulomb-attenuating method (CAM-B3LYP),[32] were employed as implemented in the GAUSSIAN 09 program package.[33] These methods were selected for the calculation of the structural details and vibrational properties of the structural models shown in Fig. 6. The electronic structure of the atoms participating in the investigated structures are described by the Dunning Gaussian type (GTO) cc-pVDZ (correlation consistent-polarized valence double zeta) basis sets.[34] For the 1st and 2nd row atoms, this basis set adds 1 s, 1p, and 1d functions. The geometries of structural models have been fully optimized at the CAM-B3LYP/TZVP level of theory using the Bery algorithm as implemented in Gaussian09 program package. All optimized geometries are characterized as stationary points on the potential energy surface with vibrational frequency calculations.

3. Results & discussion

3.1. Physicochemical characterization

The simultaneous synthesis and transfer of fluorinated graphene-like materials (see Scheme 1 in the Methods section) was carried out using various laser pulse fluence values ranging from 49 to 104 J cm⁻². The graphene-based films will be referred to as "LEST-FG-y," where "y" denotes the laser fluence used, with values including 49, 60, 74, and 104 J cm⁻². The structure and quality of the laser-assisted depositions were assessed using several microscopic and spectroscopic techniques.

The morphology of the LEST-FG-y samples is illustrated in Fig. 1. Across the entire range of laser fluences used, LEST-graphene exhibits a porous structure, as shown in the field-emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) images in Fig. 1(a-d). This porous texture results from the rapid and violent outgassing of relatively volatile oxygen and hydrogen species following the decomposition of the precursor.[35] High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM) images (see Fig. 1(e, f)) reveal that the porous graphene-like structures are composed of few-layer graphene stacks with expanded interlayer spacing. The regions labeled 1, 2, 3, and 4 in Fig. 1(e) correspond to interlayer spacings of 0.341 nm, 0.360 nm, 0.353 nm, and 0.348 nm, respectively. Fig. 1(f) corresponds to the region labeled with number 1, highlighting the few-layer stacking of the graphene sheets. These spacing values are appreciably higher than the interlayer spacing of the Bernal-stacked graphite, i.e. 0.334 nm. The x-ray diffractogram shown in Fig. S1 provides additional support to the TEM observations. Indeed, the Bragg peak which is assigned to the (002) planes is observed at ~ 25.9°, down-shifted by ~ 0.5° in comparison to the (002) Bragg peak of 2H graphite, taken from PDF # 00-041-1487 of the ICDD database. This corresponds to an interlayer spacing of 3.43 Å. This increased interlayer spacing may stem from the electronic decoupling of the graphitic layers, which occurs due to rotational disorder. Elemental analysis of the LEST-FG revealed that carbon, oxygen, and fluorine are evenly distributed, as shown by the mapping presented in Fig. 1(d-f).

The graphene quality of the synthesized LEST-FG-y electrodes was assessed using Raman spectroscopy (Fig. 2). A statistical analysis involving a sample size of 10 spectra was performed to assess how the

Fig. 1. (a-d) SEM images of LEST-FG-49, LEST-FG-60, LEST-FG-74, and LEST-FG-104, respectively. (e) HR-TEM image of LEST-FG-74, and (f) magnification of the region labeled as 1. (g-i) LEST-FG-74 elemental mapping of C, O, and F respectively.

quality of the LEST FG evolves with fluence. In all spectra, three prominent bands can be distinguished: (i) The D band (breathing mode of the C-hexagon) is observed at $\sim 1340\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The shape and area of the D band in the present spectra manifests an appreciable density of defects. This outcome is reasonably anticipated considering the porous-like morphology of the LEST-FG structures. (ii) The G band arising from the stretching (tangential) mode of all sp^2 carbons, in both rings and chains, [36] is located at $\sim 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$. (iii) The second-order 2D band appears at $\sim 2680\text{ cm}^{-1}$, arising from the E_{2g} mode, which is also present in sp^2 carbon networks. Fig. 2(a) shows representative Raman spectra of the

samples prepared with each of the four laser fluences used in the current study, as well as of a bare carbon fiber paper substrate. Unlike LEST-FG-y, the Raman spectrum of the substrate is typical of graphite, as the D band is nearly absent and the 2D band is a doublet, which testifies for its Bernal-type stacking. The low degree of overlap between the D and G bands, concurrent with their small width, is indicative of high crystallinity in LEST-FG-y samples. [37] A typical fitting of Raman spectra with Lorentzian lines (see Fig. 2(b)), reveals the presence of a low intensity band situated between the D and G bands. This new band has been assigned to the presence of finite size of crystallites, an immediate

Fig. 2. (a) Representative Raman spectra of LEST-FG- y ($y = 49, 60, 74,$ and 104 J cm^{-2}). (b) Typical fitting of a Raman spectrum of LEST-FG-74, (c) Fluence dependence of the mean FWHM of G and 2D bands. (d) Fluence dependence of the mean D/G and 2D/G band area ratios. The error bars denote the standard deviation obtained after a statistical analysis of $N = 10$ spectra.

consequence of abundant defects.[38] Alternatively, this band has been assigned to interstitial defects associated with amorphous sp^2 -bonded clusters that may include functional groups.[39,40].

Fig. 2(a) and 2(d) shows that there is a slight but monotonous increase in the D/G area ratio, which indicates an increasing density of defects upon increasing the laser fluence. The moderately broad 2D band, which marginally broadens with fluence (as shown in Fig. 2(c)), indicates the formation of graphitic stacks consisting of few-layered arrangements. The latter do not adopt a Bernal-stacked configuration, as evidenced by the symmetric shape of the 2D band. This band can be adequately fitted with a single Lorentzian curve (Fig. 2(b)), which indicates the presence of turbostratic stacking, caused by either rotational disorder or expanded interlayer spacing.[20] The mean full-width at half-maximum (FWHM) of the G band remains nearly constant, with a shallow minimum at 63 cm^{-1} (at 60 J cm^{-2}). This suggests that this particular fluence level may yield carbon of better quality, although the relationship between FWHM of the G band and fluence exhibits minimal dependency. Finally, the mean area ratio of the 2D/G bands (approximately 0.75) appears to exhibit no significant variation with fluence.

Surface chemistry and elemental analysis of the LEST-FG films were explored with XPS (Fig. 3). The wide survey spectrum obtained from the precursor (Fig. 3(a)) corresponds to FEP, i.e., the polymer component of the two outer layers. It indicates the presence of carbon and fluorine, with an atomic F:C ratio of $\sim 1.7:1$ (see Table 1). The detailed analysis of the XP spectrum of PI (intermediate layer), reported in our previous work,[25] shows the presence of C, O, and N with atomic percentage concentrations of 71.7 %, 21.6 %, and 6.7 at.%, respectively. The C1s (Fig. 3(b)) peak of FEP is analyzed into three components at binding energies of 289.4, 291.2 and 293.3 eV assigned to CF-CF₃, CF₂ and CF₃, respectively. The F1s peak is centered at 688.7 eV (Fig. 3(c)).

The wide survey spectra of the LEST-FG- y depositions are shown in Fig. 3(d), where the detected elements are carbon, oxygen, and fluorine (see Table 1 for the atomic % composition). In the XP spectrum of LEST-FG-49, the peaks of the Mo substrate are also observable. The C1s photoemission peaks of LEST-FG-49, LEST-FG-60, LEST-FG-74, and LEST-FG-104 are presented in Fig. 3(e), 3(g), 3(i), and 3(k), respectively. Six carbon components are observed for each spectrum. The sp^2 and sp^3 components are centered at 284.4 eV and 285.2 eV, whereas the C-OH/C-O-C, C = O/C-F, and COOH components are found at 286.2 eV, 287.7 eV, and 288.8 eV, respectively. According to previous reports,[41,42] the carbonyl and the C-F bonds are observed at similar binding energy. Therefore, the component at 287.7 eV may include contributions from both species. Finally, the satellite peak at 290.7 eV is assigned to $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions, present in aromatic systems. The C1s band percentage contributions are presented in Table 1. It is observed that the atomic percentage of the sp^3 component in LEST-FG-49 is two times higher than that obtained for the higher fluences utilized. This finding indicates suboptimal precursor decomposition for this low laser fluence. Also, the sp^2/sp^3 carbon ratio reaches its maximum value of 12.8 for LEST-FG-60.

The F1s photoemission peaks of LEST-FG-49, LEST-FG-60, LEST-FG-74, and LEST-FG-104 are provided in Fig. 3(f), 3(h), 3(j), and 3(l), respectively. The F1s peak of LEST-FG-49 (Fig. 3(f)) is centered at 687.8 eV, i.e. at a slightly lower binding energy in comparison to the F1s peak of the precursor (Fig. 3(c)), which is located at 688.7 eV. This peak is due to C-CF₂-C,[41] suggesting that the decomposition of FEP is not complete in the case of LEST-FG-49. The F1s peak for LEST-FG-60 and LEST-FG-74/104 is observed at 686.4 eV and 686.8 eV, respectively, and is assigned to C-F semi-ionic bonding.[41] The semi-ionic C-F bond is an intermediate state between the covalent bond, which involves bonding of fluorine to sp^3 carbon, and the ionic bond, which describes the

Fig. 3. (a) Wide survey spectrum, and (b, c) C1s, F1s photoemission peaks of FEP layer of the precursor. (d) Wide survey spectra of LEST-FG- y ($y = 49, 60, 74, 104$). C1s and F1s photoemission peaks for LEST-FG-49 (e, f), LEST-FG-60. (g, h), LEST-FG-74 (i, j), and LEST-FG-104 (k, l), respectively.

interaction between F and graphitic sp^2 carbon atoms.[6] These findings agree with the work function measurements performed with UPS (Fig. S2). We observe that increasing the laser fluence, causes decrease of the work function of LEST-FG- y . This is attributed to variations of the fluorine atomic concentration and to the different nature of the C-F chemical bonding (polarity).[43] A more detailed description is reported in the [supplementary information](#).

LEST-FG-49 exhibits the highest F content (5.5 at%), as shown in Table 1. However, this arises from the incomplete decomposition of the

FEP precursor and the transfer of unmodified FEP particles to the substrate. In the LEST-FG-60 sample, F comprises 1.6 at.% of the sample, and becomes double for the fluences of 74 J cm^{-2} and 104 J cm^{-2} . Additionally, the F/O ratio decreases with fluence. The 60 J cm^{-2} laser pulse fluence is inadequate to fully transform the precursor material. In particular, the laser beam cannot decompose the top component of the three-layered FEP//PI//FEP precursor. As a result, the top FEP layer remains incompletely decomposed and untransferred, leaving only the bottom FEP layer contributing to fluorination. Increasing the laser

Table 1

Elemental and C1s component concentrations of the LEST-FG-y films obtained by the XPS analysis.

Element	FEP	LEST-FG-49	LEST-FG-60	LEST-FG-74	LEST-FG-104
% C	36.9	90.5	96.4	90.0	88.8
% O	–	4.0	2.0	6.7	7.9
% F	63.1	5.5	1.6	3.3	3.3
C/O	–	22.62	48.20	13.43	11.24
F/C	1.71	0.06	0.02	0.04	0.04
F/O	–	1.38	0.80	0.49	0.41
C1s component		LEST-FG-49	LEST-FG-60	LEST-FG-74	LEST-FG-104
% sp ²		68.3	80.4	74.7	76.8
% sp ³		13.1	6.3	8.9	6.6
% C-OH/C-O-C		10.6	6.6	8.3	8.4
% C=O/C-F		5.5	4.1	4.7	5.5
COOH		2.5	2.6	3.4	2.7
sp ² /sp ³		5.2	12.8	8.4	11.6

fluence, provides adequate energy to decompose the whole irradiated volume of the precursor laminate. Hence, both FEP layers contribute to the fluorination of the graphene sheets.

Although spectroscopic characterization offers valuable insight on the electronic properties of materials, sheet resistance serves to extract information about electronic conductivity at a macroscopic level. This aspect becomes more critical in real-world applications because, irrespective of how low the “local” or in-flake resistance might be, factors such as junction resistance among particles could govern the resulting electronic conductivity. Comparing the measured sheet resistance values of LEST-FG-y (Fig. S3) with the ones that were obtained in our previous report on the LEST process using pure PI foil (~1.5 kOhm sq⁻¹, for the neat graphene-like film), [25] it is concluded that the addition of fluorine does not negatively affect the macroscopic conductivity of the films. Indirectly, the absence of covalent C-F bonding can be inferred because otherwise, the decreased content of sp² hybridized carbon, in favor of sp³ hybridization, would lead to a decline in the sheet resistance. However, in the case of LEST-FG-104, the sheet resistance is found to be double than that of the samples prepared with lower fluence, which is somehow expected given that this sample exhibits the highest degree of defects according to the Raman spectra. The higher sheet resistance and D/G Raman band ratio observed in LEST-FG-104, coupled with the fact that both LEST-FG-74 and LEST-FG-104 exhibit the same fluorine atomic content, demonstrate the superiority of LEST-FG-74. Additionally, the selection of a lower laser beam fluence, as in the case of LEST-FG-74, avoids potential degradation of the acceptor substrate caused by the transmitted laser beam, further supporting its preference over LEST-FG-104.

To elucidate the impact of fluorine-doping on the electrochemical behavior of the zinc-ion capacitor (ZIC) system, a control device, using neat graphene structures in its cathode, was fabricated, and compared to the fluorinated one. The control electrode, labeled as LEST-G-74, was fabricated using pure PI as the precursor irradiated at a fluence of 74 J cm⁻². In our previously reported study, [28] we have found that LEST-G-74 exhibits similar C/O ratio and hydroxyl/carboxyl carbon concentration with the LEST-FG-74 material. The specific surface area (SSA) of the former is approximately 95 m²/g, whereas the SSA of LEST-FG-74 is found to be appreciably higher, i.e. 144 m²/g. Both the neat fluorine-free and the fluorinated material are characterized as predominantly macroporous, whereas the isotherms and the pore size distribution curves, shown in Fig. S4, suggest the existence of a larger fraction of mesopores in LEST-FG-74, in comparison to LEST-G-74. This observation suggests a potential enhancement in the electrolyte ions within LEST-FG-74, in comparison to the fluorine-free graphene-like structures. The above findings align with previous studies on fluorine-doped carbons, which suggest that the incorporation of fluorine species induces additional strain on the carbon matrix, consequently increasing the specific surface area. [44,45] Concluding the physicochemical characterization of the electrodes, it is pertinent to highlight the role of the wettability of the

porous films. The wettability is particularly significant for energy storage devices operating in aqueous electrolytes. As depicted in Fig. S5 the incorporation of ~ 3.3 at.% fluorine into the graphene-like structures increases the contact angle from 121° to 143°.

3.2. Electrochemical characterization

The ZICs were electrochemically assessed in the potential window of 0.2 – 1.6 V vs Zn²⁺/Zn. Fig. 4(a, b) shows the cyclic voltammograms (CVs) that were acquired for various scan rates ranging from 0.01 V s⁻¹ to 0.5 V s⁻¹, for the ZIC utilizing the fluorine-doped and fluorine-free cathode (LEST-G-74, reference electrode). The shape of the obtained curves is a superimposition of redox peaks on a quasi-rectangle, which is typical for a hybrid capacitor comprised of one capacitive-type electrode and one battery-type electrode. In the case of LEST-FG-74, the redox peaks are more prominent, in relation to LEST-G-74. In addition, a new redox couple (noted as O₂/R₂) emerges for LEST-FG-74. Because the O₂/R₂ couple is absent from the CV curves of Fig. 4(b), it can be associated to Faradaic charge transfer reactions related with the interaction of zinc cations with fluorine. Based on the comparative CV curves of the two devices in Fig. 4(c), it is evident that LEST-FG-74 is superior, as its enclosed CV area is significantly larger. Both ZICs using a LEST-FG-74 and a LEST-G-74 cathode are substantially better than a ZIC using a bare (without LEST-graphene deposition) C paper cathode. Beyond the appearance of the reversible O₂/R₂ redox peaks, it is observed that the R₃ reduction peak is more prominent in LEST-FG-74. Comparing the CVs acquired at 0.02 V s⁻¹ and at 0.1 V s⁻¹ for LEST-FG-74, it is evident that the peak current response of the oxidation peak O₂ increases faster in comparison to that of O₁ as the applied scan rate increases. The redox pair O₁/R₁, observed in both ZICs at ~ 1 V vs Zn²⁺/Zn is due to the oxidation/reduction occurring at the zinc anode, i.e. zinc stripping (O₁) and plating (R₁). In addition, the CV broadening near the O₁/R₁ pair might arise from surface redox reactions involving the hydroxyl (C-OH) and carboxyl (O = C-OH) species, as these functional groups are present in both the fluorinated and the fluorine-free cathodes. The mechanism mentioned above can be described by the following electrochemical reactions: [46–49]

As mentioned above, the O₂/R₂ manifests an electrochemical reaction involving the fluorine chemical species. The reasoning behind this is linked to the capability of the C-F bond to coordinate with metal cations (such as Zn²⁺) because of the electrostatic interaction arising from its significant polarization. [14,27] This assignment agrees with the findings of a recent report studying fluorine/oxygen co-doped carbon nanotubes as a zinc-ion capacitor cathode. [42] In that work, reversible changes in the F1s photoemission peak intensity and binding energy during the charging and discharging of the zinc-ion hybrid capacitor was observed using ex-situ XPS. This observation was described with the following fluorine-involving electrochemical redox reaction: [42]

To gain insight into the kinetics of the reactions occurring at the electrodes of the LEST-FG-74 ZIC cathode, the peak currents of the peaks O₁/R₁, O₂/R₂, and R₃ were correlated to the applied scan rate through a power-law function of the form $I = av^b$, where a and b are adjustable parameters. [50] The values of b parameter for O₁ and R₃ i.e. 0.51 and 0.56, respectively, indicate diffusion-limited reactions. On the contrary, the b values of R₁, O₂, and R₂ approach unity (amounting to 0.85, 0.78, and 0.77, respectively), indicating a surface-controlled (capacitive) mechanism. [51] The divergence of these b values from unity is due to

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammograms of ZIC at various scan rates, using (a) the LEST-FG-74 cathode, and (b) the LEST-G-74 cathode. (c) Comparison of the devices employing LEST-FG-74, LEST-G-74, and bare C paper cathodes at scan rates of 0.02 V s^{-1} , and 0.1 V s^{-1} . (d) Double log plot of current against scan rate for LEST-FG-74, from which the b values are derived by the equation $I = av^b$. (e, f) Galvanostatic charging/discharging of ZIC with LEST-FG-74 and LEST-G-74 cathode for various applied current densities, (g) areal discharge capacity versus current density, and (h) comparative Ragone plots of the ZICs.

the increase in the ohmic contribution at high scan rates,[50] which results to a slightly decreased peak current response.

Galvanostatic charging/discharging (GCD) curves, obtained at different applied current densities, are presented in Fig. 4(e, f) for the case of LEST-FG-74 and LEST-G-74, and in Fig. S6 for the case of a ZIC using a bare carbon paper cathode. Due to the non-linear behavior exhibited by the curves, it is more accurate to utilize capacity, rather than capacitance, as a more reliable performance metric.[52] The dependence of the areal capacity on the applied current, calculated using Equation (1), is shown in Fig. 4(g). For the current density of 1 mA cm^{-2} the discharge capacity of the ZICs is $19.5 \mu\text{Ah cm}^{-2}$ for the LEST-FG-74, $14.2 \mu\text{Ah cm}^{-2}$ for the LEST-G-74, and $1.7 \mu\text{Ah cm}^{-2}$ for the bare C paper cathode. As depicted in Fig. 4(h), the ZIC operating with the LEST-FG-74 cathode delivers an energy density of 10.93 and $2.56 \mu\text{Wh cm}^{-2}$ at a power density of 92 and $6422 \mu\text{W cm}^{-2}$ respectively. In comparison to the device using the non-fluorinated LEST-G-74 cathode, the zinc-ion hybrid capacitor using the F-doped LEST-FG-74 cathode delivers 55–200 % higher energy density at the same power density. If a bare carbon fiber paper is used as a cathode, the performance of the ZIC is much lower, as expected, delivering an energy density of 0.79 and $0.04 \mu\text{Wh cm}^{-2}$ at a power density of 53 and $1650 \mu\text{W cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

While the approximately 50 % increase in the specific surface area (SSA) of the fluorinated graphene-like structures compared to neat LEST-graphene likely contributes significantly to the performance enhancement, the Faradaic charge transfer associated with the C-F bonds is also important for the observed improvement in the energy density of the device. According to literature presented in Table S1, such an enhancement is within the typical reported range.[42,44,53,54] Na *et al.* utilized a three-electrode system to demonstrate that specific capacitance of fluorination N-doped carbon nanofibers were increased by 20.5 %.[44] Further, Chen *et al.* compared two ZICs reporting that a F/O co-doped carbon nanotube-based cathode exhibits higher performance by $\sim 44.6 \%$ (in terms of capacitance) in relation to an oxygen-functionalized cathode.[42] Zhou *et al.* compared a symmetric micro-flexible capacitor using graphene-like electrodes doped with 3 % at. F and 19 at. % O, with the same configuration consisting of graphene-like electrodes with roughly half (10 %) the oxygen content, revealing a $\sim 53 \%$ enhancement for the former case.[53] Jin *et al.* used a three-electrode configuration to evaluate graphene aerogel co-doped by 4.5 at.% F and 8.3 at.% O. Fluorine was present mainly via C-F semi-ionic bonding, and the electrode showed capacitance which is by a factor of two higher than that of a graphene aerogel containing 10.5 at.% O.[54] In the comparative Ragone plots depicted in Fig. 4(h), we also include a symmetric electric double layer capacitor (EDLC) previously reported by our group. This inclusion aims to reveal the energy density advantage achieved by opting for a ZIC configuration over a symmetric one.[28].

The results obtained from electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) are presented in Fig. 5(a-d), where LEST-FG-74 and LEST-G-74 are compared. Based on Fig. 5(a, b), it becomes evident that the charge transfer resistance, associated with the diameter of the semicircle in the high-frequency regime of the Nyquist plots, increases with waiting time, for both devices. This well documented behavior is associated to the progressive corrosion of the Zn^0 anode, a common occurrence in both devices, upon exposure to the mildly acidic aqueous electrolyte.[55] In the low frequency region, the slope of the Nyquist plots is similar for the devices studied immediately post-assembly and that measured 23 h thereafter. This finding indicates that the capacitive behavior of the devices does not change during this time interval. Fig. 5(c, d) compare the electrochemical impedance spectra of the devices, acquired immediately after their assembly, to minimize the influence of corrosion on the Zn anode. Based on the analysis of the high/medium frequency region of the Nyquist plot (Fig. 5(c)), it is evident that the “semicircle” of LEST-FG-74 is larger than that of LEST-G-74. Therefore, the charge transfer resistance, R_{ct} , observed in the fluorinated cathode is higher,

likely because of the occurrence of additional processes involving Faradaic charge transfer across the electrode/electrolyte interface. This agrees with the cyclic voltammograms results, where LEST-FG-74 exhibited more charge transfer processes than LEST-G-74. From the inset of Fig. 5(c), it can be inferred that the electrode resistance does not increase in the presence of fluorine, as both curves intersect the horizontal axis at $\sim 2.6 \text{ Ohm}$. This agrees with the sheet resistance measurements, which resulted in similar values for both LEST-G-74 and LEST-FG-74. Concerning the low frequency region, the slope of the Nyquist curve, recorded from the LEST-FG-74 device is higher indicating the superiority of LEST-FG-74 over LEST-G-74 as the capacitive electrode for a Zn-ion hybrid supercapacitor. The comparison of the Bode plots is shown in Fig. 5(d). The phase angle at the lowest frequency (near 0.01 Hz) is -75.6° and -79.5° for LEST-G-74 and LEST-FG-74, respectively. The characteristic relaxation time, where the resistive and capacitive components of the entire impedance become equal, is approximately 1.95 s and 4.65 s for LEST-G-74 and LEST-FG-74, respectively. This is the minimum time interval necessary for each device to provide its energy with an efficiency higher than 50 %.[56].

The long-term cycling stability of the zinc-ion hybrid capacitors, assessed over 10,000 cycles at 2 mA cm^{-2} , was determined by monitoring the retention of discharge capacity, energy density, and power density. It was observed that the device retained approximately 57 % and 65 % of its initial capacity and energy density, respectively, whereas its power density increased by 12 % (Fig. 5(e)). These percentage capacity/energy density retentions are $\sim 6 \%$ lower than those of ZICs using a neat LEST-G-74 cathode (see Fig. S6). This finding suggests that the stability of the LEST-FG-74 cathode is slightly inferior to that of LEST-G-74. In both devices, the majority of capacity/energy fading occurs within the initial 500 cycles, likely attributed to the corrosion of the Zn anode (see inset of Fig. S7), whereas a more gradual decrease in performance takes place in the following cycles.

To verify if the marginally lower stability of LEST-FG-74 is linked to a reduced Faradaic contribution from the C-F groups, we examined both cyclic voltammetry and *ex-situ* XPS on the cycled LEST-FG-74 cathode. As depicted in the comparative CV curves of Fig. S7, there is a significant suppression of the fluorine-associated O_2/R_2 redox couple after extended cycling of LEST-FG-74. This could suggest either a gradual decrease in F-doping in the graphene-like cathode or might indicate a not entirely reversible electrochemical process. The *ex-situ* XPS findings, summarized in Fig. S8, suggest that fluorine is almost eradicated after the cycling test, with a reduction from $\sim 3.3 \text{ at. \%}$ to $\sim 0.5 \text{ at. \%}$. Simultaneously, the oxygen content experiences a significant increase (from approximately 6.6 % to about 13.5 %) after completing 10,000 operating cycles, while carbon and zinc are detected at 82.2 at. % and 3.8 at. %, respectively in the cycled LEST-FG-74 electrode. Notably, this oxygen enrichment manifests in the form of hydroxyl/epoxy functional groups, as evidenced by the corresponding component in the C1s photoemission peak, which increases threefold (from 8.3 % to 24.5 %) compared to the as-prepared LEST-FG-74. The formation of epoxy species is further supported by our DFT study, as discussed in the following section. The remaining C1s components of the cycled LEST-FG-74 cathode include the following species: 57.7 % sp^2 carbon, 9.6 % sp^3 carbon, 5.4 % C=O/C-F, and 2.8 % carboxyls. Considering the Zn content, the $\text{Zn}2\text{p}_{3/2}$ photoemission and the Auger LVV peaks, are located at 1023.6 eV and 985.9 eV, respectively. The spectra analysis revealed a modified Auger parameter of 2009.5 eV, which suggests the formation of zinc hydroxide species on the cycled electrode surface.[57] These species are recognized to precipitate at the carbon-based cathodes of ZICs due to the pH elevation of the electrolyte.[58,59].

3.3. Insights from DFT studies

To enhance and deepen our understanding at the atomic scale, we conducted DFT simulations on various clusters representative of the material under study, based on compositional information provided by

Fig. 5. Nyquist plots of ZIC incorporating (a) LEST-FG-74 as the cathode, and (b) LEST-G-74 as the cathode. Comparative (c) Nyquist plots, and (d) Bode plots of the ZICs, recorded immediately after their assembly, (e) evolution of the capacity, energy density and power density versus the number of cycles performed, for the case of the ZIC using a LEST-FG-74 cathode.

XPS. This computational approach has provided additional evidence supporting the various structural details suggested by our experimental observations. The investigation followed a hierarchical approach to elucidate the characteristics of chemical interactions between fluorine atoms, oxygen-containing species, and graphene flakes. Subsequently, as XPS analysis has revealed the presence of Zn species, from the electrolyte solution, on cycled LEST-FG-74, we explored the interactions of Zn^{2+} ions with the graphene layer decorated with fluorine and oxygen species.

Fig. 6 illustrates some typical structural models representing the initial and optimized configurations from the DFT studies. A symmetric arrangement of seven benzol rings was selected as the basis for the graphene element. Although alternative structural models could be used as starting configurations, the selected models are representative of the material's composition, ensuring that the DFT results from these clusters encompass the essential processes. Oxygen and fluorine species were positioned on the basal plane carbon atoms, rather than directly on the edge atoms, where hydrogen was used for stabilization. Cluster A represents a few atoms snapshot of the as-prepared F-doped graphene where the presence of oxidic species is inevitable, as also demonstrated by the XPS analysis. Clusters B and C represent possible bonding preferences for the Zn^{2+} ion approaching the F-doped graphene electrode. For cluster B, a Zn^{2+} ion is positioned in the proximity of the graphene layer, while for cluster C, a Zn^{2+} ion is placed nearby the heteroatoms decorating the graphene surface.

The main conclusions emanating from the DFT studies are outlined as follows. Hydroxy groups ($-\text{OH}$) and fluorine atoms can be covalently bonded to the graphene layer, transforming a carbon atom from sp^2 to sp^3 hybridization. While $-\text{OH}$ groups can only form covalent bonds with carbon atoms, a fluorine atom can also form a semi-ionic bond with an

sp^2 carbon atom without altering the hybridization state of the carbon atom. Analyzing the binding energies, it becomes evident that covalent bonding is more stable than semi-ionic bonding. As shown in Fig. 6 (A-optimized), fluorine is prone to interact via hydrogen bonding with the hydrogen atoms of nearby hydroxy groups.

Covalent and/or semi-ionic bonded fluorine atoms may detach from the graphene layers in the presence of adjacent hydrogen atoms in $-\text{OH}$ groups. Simultaneously, hydrogen atoms may detach from oxygen in $-\text{OH}$ groups; in this case, the oxygen atoms transform into epoxy groups. Further, the calculations indicate that fluorine can be separated from the graphene layer after interacting with the hydrogen atom of the hydroxy group. The detached fluorine-hydrogen species can then dissolve as ions into the electrolyte solution in contact with the electrode surface. Simulations regarding the presence of Zn^{2+} demonstrate that these ions can interact with fluorine atoms, forming relevant species. Alternatively, Zn can covalently bond with oxygen on the electrode's surface, forming zinc oxo species. This DFT result provides strong support for the experimental findings that the fluorine heteroatoms on graphene significantly reduce after prolonged cycling, while simultaneously zinc oxo species form on the electrode's surface.

4. Conclusions

In summary, our study represents a paradigm shift in the synthesis of fluorinated graphene-like films, utilizing laser-assisted technology to simultaneously decompose diverse polymer precursors (FEP/PI/FEP laminate) and transfer the graphene-like material onto the current collector; thereby creating the electrode in a single step. The resulting porous fluorinated graphene films consists of few-layer graphene layers with turbostratic stacking. We observed that the quality of the produced materials, in terms of both carbon and fluorine content, moderately depends on the lasing conditions, showing a slight improvement in quality at a fluence of 74 J cm^{-2} . For the particular precursor used, this fluence results in fluorine content of ~ 3.3 at %. XPS analysis revealed a semi-ionic C-F bonding, and a C/O ratio of ~ 13.4 . Notably, our laser-assisted fluorinated graphene emerges as a preferred choice for supercapacitor electrode fabrication, demonstrating remarkable performance metrics. The fluorinated graphene-like electrodes were explored as the cathode of a zinc-ion hybrid capacitor.

Comparison with a non-fluorinated graphene cathode revealed a significant improvement in the ZIC performance of the F-doped graphene. The performance enhancement was attributed to the interaction between Zn^{2+} and the F-doped graphene, as well as to the approximately 50 % increase in specific surface area compared to the undoped graphene cathode. Specifically, the F-doped ZIC exhibited a discharge capacity of $19.5 \mu\text{Ah cm}^{-2}$ at 1 mA cm^{-2} , delivering an energy density of $10.93 \mu\text{Wh cm}^{-2}$ at a power density of $92 \mu\text{W cm}^{-2}$. After undergoing 10,000 operating cycles, it retained 65 % of its initial energy density.

Additionally, DFT simulations provided atomic-scale insights that support our experimental observations. Specifically, DFT studies of various selected clusters, representing realistic local bonding configurations of the material, elucidated the bonding interactions between fluorine atoms, oxygen-containing species, and graphene flakes. The DFT data also shed light on the degradation mechanisms of the device under long-term operation, which were corroborated by XPS analysis of the cycled electrode, *post mortem*. The DFT studies revealed that Zn species from the electrolyte solution exhibit strong interactions with Zn^{2+} ions and the graphene layer decorated with fluorine and oxygen species. This interaction can effectively remove fluorine species from the graphene scaffold. Additionally, Zn can covalently bond with oxygen on the electrode's surface, forming zinc oxo species.

In summary, the F-doped graphene electrode method developed in this work offers several advantages over traditional chemical processes, providing a simplified and eco-friendly alternative that avoids the complexities associated with the use of additives, binders, and the need for extensive post-treatment. This method addresses and mitigates the

Fig. 6. Ball-and-stick draws of the initial and optimized structural models at the CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVDZ level of theory. A. A possible arrangement of the as-prepared material. B. Approaching of a Zn^{2+} ion near the stabilized structure of Cluster A. C. A Zn^{2+} ion positioned near two heteroatoms (F atom and ionized $-\text{O}^-$ hydroxy group) bound to the graphene layer, set to interact with both at an effective distance.

environmental concerns typically associated with conventional techniques. Moreover, the integration of laser technology with AI methodologies underscores its digital compatibility, facilitating scalability to an industrial level. This convergence of advanced techniques heralds a new era in the production of high-quality graphene-related materials, characterized by enhanced efficiency, sustainability, and enhanced performance. Additionally, augmented by DFT studies, our current findings offer a comprehensive understanding of the material's behavior and the factors influencing its performance and stability. These insights provide valuable guidance for the safe and sustainable by design and optimization of future graphene-based energy storage devices.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Nikolaos Samartzis: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Kapil Bhorkar:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Labrini Sygellou:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Elli Bellou:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Nikos Boukos:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Athanasios Chrissanthopoulos:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Spyros N. Yannopoulos:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2025.160505>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] S. Ghosh, S. Barg, S.M. Jeong, K. (Ken) Ostrikov, Heteroatom-Doped and Oxygen-Functionalized Nanocarbons for High-Performance Supercapacitors, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 10 (2020) 2001239, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202001239>.
- [2] S. Srivastava, S.K. Jain, G. Gupta, T.D. Senguttuvan, B.K. Gupta, Boron-doped few-layer graphene nanosheet gas sensor for enhanced ammonia sensing at room temperature, *RSC Adv.* 10 (2020) 1007–1014, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9RA08707A>.
- [3] J.T. Robinson, J.S. Burgess, C.E. Junkermeier, S.C. Badescu, T.L. Reinecke, F. K. Perkins, M.K. Zalalutdniov, J.W. Baldwin, J.C. Culbertson, P.E. Sheehan, E. S. Snow, Properties of Fluorinated Graphene Films, *Nano Lett.* 10 (2010) 3001–3005, <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl101437p>.
- [4] S. Kwon, J.-H. Ko, K.-J. Jeon, Y.-H. Kim, J.Y. Park, Enhanced Nanoscale Friction on Fluorinated Graphene, *Nano Lett.* 12 (2012) 6043–6048, <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl204019k>.
- [5] D. Damien, P.M. Sudeep, T.N. Narayanan, M.R. Anantharaman, P.M. Ajayan, M. M. Shajjumon, Fluorinated graphene based electrodes for high performance primary lithium batteries, *RSC Adv.* 3 (2013) 25702, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c3ra45377d>.
- [6] J. Kim, R. Zhou, K. Murakoshi, S. Yasuda, Advantage of semi-ionic bonding in fluorine-doped carbon materials for the oxygen evolution reaction in alkaline media, *RSC Adv.* 8 (2018) 14152–14156, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8RA01636D>.
- [7] H. Touhara, F. Okino, Property control of carbon materials by fluorination, *Carbon* n. y. 38 (2000) 241–267, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0008-6223\(99\)00140-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0008-6223(99)00140-2).
- [8] S. Zhou, S.D. Sherpa, D.W. Hess, A. Bongiorno, Chemical Bonding of Partially Fluorinated Graphene, *J. Phys. Chem. c* 118 (2014) 26402–26408, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp508965q>.
- [9] J.H. Lee, G.K.W. Koon, D.W. Shin, V.E. Fedorov, J.-Y. Choi, J.-B. Yoo, B. Özyilmaz, Property Control of Graphene by Employing “Semi-Ionic” Liquid Fluorination, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 23 (2013) 3329–3334, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201202822>.
- [10] W. Feng, P. Long, Y. Feng, Y. Li, Two-Dimensional Fluorinated Graphene: Synthesis, Structures, Properties and Applications, *Adv. Sci.* 3 (2016) 1500413, <https://doi.org/10.1002/advs.201500413>.
- [11] R.R. Nair, W. Ren, R. Jalil, I. Riaz, V.G. Kravets, L. Britnell, P. Blake, F. Schedin, A. S. Mayorov, S. Yuan, M.I. Katsnelson, H.-M. Cheng, W. Strupinski, L.G. Bulusheva, A.V. Okotrub, I.V. Grigorieva, A.N. Grigorenko, K.S. Novoselov, A.K. Geim, Fluorographene: A Two-Dimensional Counterpart of Teflon, *Small* 6 (2010) 2877–2884, <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.201001555>.
- [12] R. Yang, L. Zhang, Y. Wang, Z. Shi, D. Shi, H. Gao, E. Wang, G. Zhang, An Anisotropic Etching Effect in the Graphene Basal Plane, *Adv. Mater.* 22 (2010) 4014–4019, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201000618>.
- [13] C.S. Lim, Z. Sofer, J. Plutnar, M. Pumera, Fluorographenes for Energy and Sensing Application: The Amount of Fluorine Matters, *ACS Omega* 3 (2018) 17700–17706, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.8b02582>.
- [14] T. Wang, X. Zang, X. Wang, X. Gu, Q. Shao, N. Cao, Recent advances in fluorine-doped/fluorinated carbon-based materials for supercapacitors, *Energy Storage Mater.* 30 (2020) 367–384, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ensm.2020.04.044>.
- [15] H. Chang, J. Cheng, X. Liu, J. Gao, M. Li, J. Li, X. Tao, F. Ding, Z. Zheng, Facile Synthesis of Wide-Bandgap Fluorinated Graphene Semiconductors, *Chem. - A Eur. J.* 17 (2011) 8896–8903, <https://doi.org/10.1002/chem.201100699>.
- [16] R. Zbořil, F. Karlický, A.B. Bourlino, T.A. Steriotis, A.K. Stubos, V. Georgakilas, K. Sařárová, D. Jančík, C. Trapalis, M. Otyepka, Graphene Fluoride: A Stable Stoichiometric Graphene Derivative and its Chemical Conversion to Graphene, *Small* 6 (2010) 2885–2891, <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.201001401>.
- [17] P. Gong, Z. Wang, J. Wang, H. Wang, Z. Li, Z. Fan, Y. Xu, X. Han, S. Yang, One-pot sonochemical preparation of fluorographene and selective tuning of its fluorine coverage, *J. Mater. Chem.* 22 (2012) 16950, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c2jm32294c>.
- [18] M. Zhu, X. Xie, Y. Guo, P. Chen, X. Ou, G. Yu, M. Liu, Fluorographene nanosheets with broad solvent dispersibility and their applications as a modified layer in organic field-effect transistors, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 15 (2013) 20992, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c3cp53383b>.
- [19] M.F. El-Kady, V. Strong, S. Dubin, R.B. Kaner, Laser Scribing of High-Performance and Flexible Graphene-Based Electrochemical Capacitors, *Science* (80-.). 335 (2012) 1326–1330, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1216744>.
- [20] N. Samartzis, M. Athanasiou, V. Dracopoulos, S.N. Yannopoulos, T. Ioannides, Laser-assisted transformation of a phenol-based resin to high quality graphene-like powder for supercapacitor applications, *Chem. Eng. J.* 430 (2022) 133179, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.133179>.
- [21] M. Athanasiou, N. Samartzis, L. Sygellou, V. Dracopoulos, T. Ioannides, S. N. Yannopoulos, High-quality laser-assisted biomass-based turbostratic graphene for high-performance supercapacitors, *Carbon* n. y. 172 (2021) 750–761, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2020.10.042>.
- [22] T.D. Le, H. Phan, S. Kwon, S. Park, Y. Jung, J. Min, B.J. Chun, H. Yoon, S.H. Ko, S. Kim, Y. Kim, Recent Advances in Laser-Induced Graphene: Mechanism, Fabrication, Properties, and Applications in Flexible Electronics, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 32 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202205158>.
- [23] R. Ye, X. Han, D.V. Kosynkin, Y. Li, C. Zhang, B. Jiang, A.A. Martí, J.M. Tour, Laser-Induced Conversion of Teflon into Fluorinated Nanodiamonds or Fluorinated Graphene, *ACS Nano* 12 (2018) 1083–1088, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.7b05877>.
- [24] Y. Li, D.X. Luong, J. Zhang, Y.R. Tarkunde, C. Kittrell, F. Sargunara, Y. Ji, C. J. Arnsch, J.M. Tour, Laser-Induced Graphene in Controlled Atmospheres: From Superhydrophilic to Superhydrophobic Surfaces, *Adv. Mater.* 29 (2017) 1700496, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201700496>.
- [25] K. Bhorkar, N. Samartzis, M. Athanasiou, L. Sygellou, N. Boukos, V. Dracopoulos, T. Ioannides, S.N. Yannopoulos, Laser-assisted explosive synthesis and transfer of turbostratic graphene-related materials for energy conversion applications, *Npj 2D Mater. Appl.* 6 (2022) 56, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41699-022-00331-7>.
- [26] N. Samartzis, M. Athanasiou, L. Sygellou, S.N. Yannopoulos, Direct Graphene Deposition via a Modified Laser-Assisted Method for Interdigitated Microflexible Supercapacitors, *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* 7 (2024) 3782–3792, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnm.3c05387>.
- [27] D. O'Hagan, Understanding organofluorine chemistry. An introduction to the C–F bond, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 37 (2008) 308–319, <https://doi.org/10.1039/B711844A>.
- [28] N. Samartzis, K. Bhorkar, M. Athanasiou, L. Sygellou, V. Dracopoulos, T. Ioannides, S.N. Yannopoulos, Direct laser-assisted fabrication of turbostratic graphene electrodes: Comparing symmetric and zinc-ion hybrid supercapacitors, *Carbon* n. y. 201 (2023) 941–951, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2022.09.076>.
- [29] A.D. Becke, Density-functional thermochemistry. III. The role of exact exchange, *J. Chem. Phys.* 98 (1993) 5648–5652, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.464913>.
- [30] P.J. Stephens, F.J. Devlin, C.F. Chabalowski, M.J. Frisch, Ab Initio Calculation of Vibrational Absorption and Circular Dichroism Spectra Using Density Functional Force Fields, *J. Phys. Chem.* 98 (1994) 11623–11627, <https://doi.org/10.1021/j100096a001>.
- [31] C. Lee, W. Yang, R.G. Parr, Development of the Colle-Salvetti correlation-energy formula into a functional of the electron density, *PhysRevB.* 37 (1988) 785–789, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.37.785>.
- [32] T. Yanai, D.P. Tew, N.C. Handy, A new hybrid exchange–correlation functional using the Coulomb-attenuating method (CAM-B3LYP), *Chem. Phys. Lett.* 393 (2004) 51–57, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cplett.2004.06.011>.
- [33] M.J. Frisch, G.W. Trucks, H.B. Schlegel, Gaussian 09, Revision A.01, (n.d.).

- [34] T.H. Dunning, Gaussian basis sets for use in correlated molecular calculations. I. The atoms boron through neon and hydrogen, *J. Chem. Phys.* 90 (1989) 1007–1023, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.456153>.
- [35] J. Lin, Z. Peng, Y. Liu, F. Ruiz-Zepeda, R. Ye, E.L.G. Samuel, M.J. Yacamán, B. I. Yakobson, J.M. Tour, Laser-induced porous graphene films from commercial polymers, *Nat. Commun.* 5 (2014) 5714, <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms6714>.
- [36] A.C. Ferrari, Raman spectroscopy of graphene and graphite: Disorder, electron–phonon coupling, doping and nonadiabatic effects, *Solid State Commun.* 143 (2007) 47–57, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssc.2007.03.052>.
- [37] A.C. Ferrari, J. Robertson, Interpretation of Raman spectra of disordered and amorphous carbon, *PhysRevB.* 61 (2000) 14095–14107, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.61.14095>.
- [38] R.J. Nemanich, S.A. Solin, First- and second-order Raman scattering from finite-size crystals of graphite, *PhysRevB.* 20 (1979) 392–401, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.20.392>.
- [39] S. Claramunt, A. Varea, D. López-Díaz, M.M. Velázquez, A. Cornet, A. Cirera, The Importance of Interbands on the Interpretation of the Raman Spectrum of Graphene Oxide, *J. Phys. Chem. c.* 119 (2015) 10123–10129, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.5b01590>.
- [40] P.A. Goodman, H. Li, Y. Gao, Y.F. Lu, J.D. Stenger-Smith, J. Redepenning, Preparation and characterization of high surface area, high porosity carbon monoliths from pyrolyzed bovine bone and their performance as supercapacitor electrodes, *Carbon n. y.* 55 (2013) 291–298, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2012.12.066>.
- [41] W. Kang, S. Li, Preparation of fluorinated graphene to study its gas sensitivity, *RSC Adv.* 8 (2018) 23459–23467, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8RA03451F>.
- [42] Q. Chen, L. Cao, H. Wang, Z. Zhou, P. Xiao, Oxygen/fluorine-functionalized flexible carbon electrodes for high-performance and anti-self-discharge Zn-ion hybrid capacitors, *J. Power Sources.* 538 (2022) 231586, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2022.231586>.
- [43] S.D. Sherpa, G. Levitin, D.W. Hess, Effect of the polarity of carbon-fluorine bonds on the work function of plasma-fluorinated epitaxial graphene, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 101 (2012) 111602, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4752443>.
- [44] W. Na, J. Jun, J.W. Park, G. Lee, J. Jang, Highly porous carbon nanofibers co-doped with fluorine and nitrogen for outstanding supercapacitor performance, *J. Mater. Chem. a.* 5 (2017) 17379–17387, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7TA04406B>.
- [45] M.-J. Jung, E. Jeong, S. Kim, S.I. Lee, J.-S. Yoo, Y.-S. Lee, Fluorination effect of activated carbon electrodes on the electrochemical performance of electric double layer capacitors, *J. Fluor. Chem.* 132 (2011) 1127–1133, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfluchem.2011.06.046>.
- [46] J. Wu, R. Liu, M. Li, X. Luo, W. Lai, X. Zhang, D. Li, F. Yu, Y. Chen, Boosting effects of hydroxyl groups on porous carbon for improved aqueous zinc-ion capacitors, *J. Energy Storage.* 48 (2022) 103996, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2022.103996>.
- [47] Y. Shao, Z. Sun, Z. Tian, S. Li, G. Wu, M. Wang, X. Tong, F. Shen, Z. Xia, V. Tung, J. Sun, Y. Shao, Regulating Oxygen Substituents with Optimized Redox Activity in Chemically Reduced Graphene Oxide for Aqueous Zn-Ion Hybrid Capacitor, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 31 (2021) 2007843, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202007843>.
- [48] L. Dong, W. Yang, W. Yang, Y. Li, W. Wu, G. Wang, Multivalent metal ion hybrid capacitors: a review with a focus on zinc-ion hybrid capacitors, *J. Mater. Chem. a.* 7 (2019) 13810–13832, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9TA02678A>.
- [49] C. Wang, X. Zeng, P.J. Cullen, Z. Pei, The rise of flexible zinc-ion hybrid capacitors: advances, challenges, and outlooks, *J. Mater. Chem. a.* 9 (2021) 19054–19082, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1TA02775A>.
- [50] V. Augustyn, J. Come, M.A. Lowe, J.W. Kim, P.-L. Taberna, S.H. Tolbert, H. D. Abruña, P. Simon, B. Dunn, High-rate electrochemical energy storage through Li + intercalation pseudocapacitance, *Nat. Mater.* 12 (2013) 518–522, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmat3601>.
- [51] H. Lindström, S. Södergren, A. Solbrand, H. Rensmo, J. Hjelm, A. Hagfeldt, S.-E. Lindquist, Li + Ion Insertion in TiO₂ (Anatase). 2. Voltammetry on Nanoporous Films, *J. Phys. Chem. b.* 101 (1997) 7717–7722, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp970490q>.
- [52] A. Noori, M.F. El-Kady, M.S. Rahmanifar, R.B. Kaner, M.F. Mousavi, Towards establishing standard performance metrics for batteries, supercapacitors and beyond, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 48 (2019) 1272–1341, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8CS00581H>.
- [53] F. Zhou, H. Huang, C. Xiao, S. Zheng, X. Shi, J. Qin, Q. Fu, X. Bao, X. Feng, K. Müllen, Z.-S. Wu, Electrochemically Scalable Production of Fluorine-Modified Graphene for Flexible and High-Energy Ionogel-Based Microsupercapacitors, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 140 (2018) 8198–8205, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.8b03235>.
- [54] T. Jin, J. Chen, C. Wang, Y. Qian, L. Lu, Facile synthesis of fluorine-doped graphene aerogel with rich semi-ionic C–F bonds for high-performance supercapacitor application, *J. Mater. Sci.* 55 (2020) 12103–12113, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-020-04821-1>.
- [55] Q. Li, L. Han, Q. Luo, X. Liu, J. Yi, Towards Understanding the Corrosion Behavior of Zinc-Metal Anode in Aqueous Systems: From Fundamentals to Strategies, *Batter. Supercaps.* 5 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1002/batt.202100417>.
- [56] Y. Shao, J. Li, Y. Li, H. Wang, Q. Zhang, R.B. Kaner, Flexible quasi-solid-state planar micro-supercapacitor based on cellular graphene films, *Mater. Horiz.* 4 (2017) 1145–1150, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7MH00441A>.
- [57] J. Duchoslav, R. Steinberger, M. Arndt, D. Stifter, XPS study of zinc hydroxide as a potential corrosion product of zinc: Rapid X-ray induced conversion into zinc oxide, *Corros. Sci.* 82 (2014) 356–361, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2014.01.037>.
- [58] Z. Li, D. Chen, Y. An, C. Chen, L. Wu, Z. Chen, Y. Sun, X. Zhang, Flexible and anti-freezing quasi-solid-state zinc ion hybrid supercapacitors based on pencil shavings derived porous carbon, *Energy Storage Mater.* 28 (2020) 307–314, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enstm.2020.01.028>.
- [59] N.J. Herrmann, H. Euchner, A. Groß, B. Horstmann, The Cycling Mechanism of Manganese-Oxide Cathodes in Zinc Batteries: A Theory-Based Approach, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 14 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202302553>.